

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Section 1: Applicants

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[further personal information removed for privacy purposes]

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	Patient signalS United in a Metabase: the PLUM Platform
Project duration (in months)	24 months

English public summary

We aim to build a community-governed machine-actionable platform that gathers hospital patient experience data from different sources, for example the Patient Experience Monitor (PEM), social media posts, sounding boards. The Patient signalS United in a Metabase (PLUM) platform gathers patient experiences to be queried and reused at scale. A built-in learning model uses intelligent trend detection and self-service analytics: a user can query the system and pull synthesised information from the system, whilst the system will also deliver information (for example weekly trends) to the user, steering health care innovation and service improvement.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 93

Dutch public summary

We willen, samen met patiënten, zorgprofessionals en andere gebruikers, een digitaal platform ontwikkelen dat ervaringen van patiënten (van het UMC Utrecht) samenbrengt die reeds beschikbaar zijn uit verschillende bronnen, zoals bijvoorbeeld de patiëntervaringsmonitor (PEM), sociale media berichten, en klankbordgroepen. Het Patient signalS United in a Metabase (PLUM) platform maakt patiëntervaringen vrij toegankelijk, doorzoekbaar en breed inzetbaar. Een ingebouwd AI-leermodel gebruikt slimme trend detectie and self-service analysetechnieken zodat a) een gebruiker de data kan doorzoeken, b) het platform zelf informatie genereert (bijvoorbeeld wekelijkse trends) en de gebruiker toestuurt. Op die manier kunnen patiëntervaringen verbetering

in de zorg en innovatie aansturen.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 99

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

We will develop a **community-driven and governed digital platform** that gathers hospital patient experiences from different sources and actively steers health care innovation and service improvement. The *'Patient Signals united in a Metabase'* (PLUM) platform, named after the first patient advisor at UMC Utrecht Nicole Plum, will be a searchable open-access repository of patient knowledge on health and healthcare systems. Cross-domain interoperability results in the collection of different hospital patient experience data, such as for example patient satisfaction questionnaires, condition-specific sounding boards, hospital complaints, etc.

Integrated learning models (e.g. large language models) will identify and inform users about, for example, health research gaps and needs, trending health topics, and patient concerns with healthcare services.

The open-source solution will be implemented at UMC Utrecht and governed by the UMC Utrecht Client Board in collaboration with the developers. PLUM will be tested at two other hospitals.

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3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

"How many times do I have to signal my concerns for you to take action?" [quote from a UMC Utrecht patient partner]

Different healthcare stakeholders (patient organisations, funders, policymakers, etc.) are committed to patient and community engagement in healthcare improvement and innovation. At UMC Utrecht (and other UMCs), patients' experiences are continuously sought via for example the patient experience monitor (PEM; a national, validated, questionnaire completed by patients after a hospital visit), the UMC Utrecht Patient Panel (> 1000 patient volunteers completing surveys at request of UMC Utrecht), and various disease-specific sounding boards. Currently, these fragmented pieces of patient information exist and are not accessible beyond those that collected the information, or worse, which existence is unknown. Despite these many unconnected initiatives, patient partners feel unheard and excluded from full participation: their input is often left with no response.

An open-access repository makes their information available for healthcare improvements, health research and innovation, which might benefit many other patients. The PLUM platform will also contain patient experience data collected via non-digital channels (for example notes from the staff at the service desk) to allow for more inclusive and diverse patient and community engagement.

Word count SEC32 (max. 200): 193

3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

The PLUM platform contributes to an open science culture of teamwork, FAIR data, accountability, integrity and transparency. Open Science is about openness about the scientific process whilst also opening the scientific process to non-academic communities.

Currently, participation of patients and citizens in the knowledge production process is stimulated and patient knowledge is being generated. What is missing, is an infrastructure, so "citizen science-generated data, knowledge, insights and practices [can be] easily gathered, hosted and aggregated [...], such that these data are integrated into mainstream processes for research, policymaking and decision-making" [1].

The PLUM platform will a) collate patient experience data from different resources, and b) be machine-actionable so patient experience data can be queried and reused at scale. In addition, we will develop a governance structure in which all relevant stakeholders have a role.

Intelligent trend detection and self-service analytics facilitate the inclusion of patient knowledge in the practice of healthcare research, innovation and improvement as early as possible (e.g. agenda-setting, identification of knowledge gaps, ...). The PLUM platform works towards making patient knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone. Using different data sources, PLUM contributes to a more diverse, **inclusive, equitable and sustainable knowledge production**.

Word count SEC33 (max. 200): 197

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

We work towards a functional PLUM platform in April 2028. In 2024, we conducted several rounds of defining and refining the needs and wishes of patients and staff and established a proof of concept. We presented PLUM to staff and patients who were unanimously supportive of the concept. Therefore, in April 2026, we can start with the following steps whilst working *agile*:

1. Develop PLUM 5 sources:

We will build a platform using Microsoft Azure cloud components as the base to which we add:

- software to facilitate cross-domain interoperability, including logic to index, AI embedding and combining data;
- interfaces to query the data using keywords and AI natural language RAG;
- dashboards and automatic reporting to summarize and present patient experiences.

We develop the data-output function, intelligent trend detection, and self-service analytics of the platform in cocreation with patients and citizens, and the dashboard and search functions in co-creation with UMCU staff. To secure an open-access data system, patient experiences must be collected safely and ethically. The PLUM sources only contain patient experience data: it is important to distinguish legal and consent prerequisites for medical patient information and patient experience data (often given outside a patient-doctor relationship). We have patient consent for two data sources: patient experience monitor (PEM) and UMCU patient panel. AJ and NN will collaborate with patient partners and consult UMCU patients how their experiences can be used in the platform and develop a suitable and feasible consent method. We will liaise with our legal team to ensure we align with GDPR and work towards an open as possible (and as closed as necessary) system that can be used by UMCU and beyond.

2. Pilot of PLUM 5 sources

We will conduct usability and feasibility tests using five sources selected by patients and end users: sounding boards, PEM, socials, conversations with users at the information desk, and the UMCU patient panel. We will select a group of staff members in sciences, education, and healthcare to test PLUM 5 sources. Testing will inform potential reconfiguration of the platform and the digital maturity of the source data whilst gaining insight in the workflow of the platform in end-users' daily practice. We will collaborate with patients and citizens to identify how they want to be informed about PLUM uptake and impact of patient experiences, resulting in a feedback-loop.

3. Minimal viable product (MVP)

Finalizing the MVP containing an interface and data platform, facilitating intelligent trend detection and self-service analytics. The MVP will be validated with patients – sharing their experiences - to ensure the platform meets their expectations.

4. Implementation and quality test

To facilitate uptake of the platform in daily practice, we will:

- a) evaluate, together with patients, whether the data sources are being used to their full extent; we will assess the quality of the generated answers in relation to the question asked.
- b) train end-users in using the platform leading towards patient focused innovations and improvements (incorporating knowledge obtained in previous step).
- c) We will assess the natural language processing performance and make improvements (if necessary) feeding the AI model with Dutch medical and patient jargon and synonyms (collaboration with developers of Lees Simpel app).

Improvements based on this test phase will be integrated in the next step.

5. Upgrading PLUM 5 to PLUM multi-sources

We will develop code for cross-domain compatibility with additional patient experience resources, for example notes from the hospital chaplain, social workers, and other non-medical information from HiX ChipSoft.

6. Piloting PLUM in two hospitals and governance structure

We aim to make PLUM available to all hospitals, and beyond. During this project, we will test PLUM in one regional and one UMC hospital. We liaised with other UMCs who have expressed interest in adopting PLUM. To ensure national governance, we will liaise with KNAW and NFU. Having a national partner to uphold and maintain the platform as intended is a sustainable way to secure FAIR data use and management (e.g. secure data transferability). Our aim for a community-driven and governed digital platform calls for a twofold governance plan (see section 5.1). First, we will develop a UMCU governance structure following several stakeholder consultations. The UMCU Patient Board supports this project and offers to take up governance leadership.

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4.2 Team composition

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4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood and impact	Risk mitigation strategy
<i>Name of the risk</i>	<i>Likelihood: (low, medium, high) Impact: (low, medium, high)</i>	<i>Describe the measures which will be taken to mitigate the risk</i>
Quality of information produced is low due to inconsistent quality of source-data.	Medium x Medium	Provide guidelines and best practices to improve the quality of source-data.
Low usage of PLUM	Medium x Medium	Actively involve end users in development
Patient experiences cannot be used due to lack of patient consent.	Medium x Medium	Especially challenging for sharing data outside UMC Utrecht. We work with the privacy officer and patients towards a general consent.
Existing AI LLMs do not have sufficient support for Dutch language	High x Medium	Using existing multi-language models for now, and switch to improved models when available
Natural Language search (using AI RAG) hallucinates answers	Low x Low	Prompt Engineering prevents creativity in answers.
Output-data is not representative for the whole of services provided within UMCU, e.g. data might be disease specific.	Low x Low	The platform shows the source of origin to maintain transparency.

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4.4 Budget

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Total Personnel requested: 235.201,44 **Total Material/IT requested:** 14.000,00 **Total budget requested:** 249.201,44

4.5 Budget justification

1) salaries and stakeholder engagement (paid patient partners):

NN and AJ, who invented the platform, will be joined by a group of experts in building PLUM platform. PLUM will be developed using an iterative, agile approach, whilst actively involving end users and other stakeholders. AJ and NN liaise with patients and staff throughout the project and lead the development of the consent model and governance structure of the platform.

The scrum team's work is organized in two-week sprints. We anticipate three full-time developers will need to run six sprints.

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We will develop infographics and a podcast or webinar (in collaboration with INVOLV) to share our work, present at the Open Science & Betweter Festival and publish two papers in peer-reviewed journal(s).

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4.6 Impact plan

Patient organisations are joint by policymakers, funders, and international organisations (WHO, WMA) in their quest for social participation in **research and healthcare development**. PLUM makes patient knowledge accessible and deployable to a wide range of scientists, in medicine and health education. University Utrecht curriculum revision teams and educators want PLUM to inform their work. UMCU divisions want to use PLUM to inform healthcare improvement and research priorities.

PLUM is developed at the request of **patients**: they want their input to be used and acted upon. PLUM will make patient knowledge broadly available and searchable; the intelligent trend detection will make patient signals visible and drive healthcare initiatives and decision-making to the benefit of (future) patients. People are increasingly engaged as partners; yet recognition and influence are variable, and too many are excluded: PLUM will include data sources from underrepresented communities.

Business intelligence plays a significant role in improving healthcare services, including UMCs. PLUM is a strategic tool that will translate patient experiences into actionable insights, essential for meeting the needs of service users, providing high quality, yet, meaningful and patient-centered care. UMCU healthcare leaders want to use PLUM to define patient-centered key performance indicators to make responsive and patient-driven decisions.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 200

Section 5: Sustainability and software management Section

5.1: Sustainability plan

We developed a two-stage sustainability plan for PLUM:

1) Sustainability within UMCU: technical maintenance and governance

Technical work is required to keep PLUM functional, for example life cycle management activities include adding and cleaning data (sources), regularly updating and upgrading software and offering maintenance and support to handle questions and unexpected failures.

To ensure long-term sustainability, the Head of Quality & Patient Safety agreed to act as business owner and cover the anticipated yearly 8% exploitation costs. The IT department has committed to allocate a dedicated product owner for the technical development and maintenance. A go/no-go on the implementation of this platform will ensure the resources needed to govern the infrastructure. Steps have been taken to ensure this structure is in place at the start of the project. (see timeline in Figure 1).

Community-driven **governance structure** of PLUM: This structure will be developed throughout the project and will be ready with the launch of the platform. Every step in the development process will be discussed with a group of UMCU patients, healthcare professionals and management. This group will also work towards a model for community-driven governance. The UMCU Client Board (Cliëntenraad) have expressed interest to take the lead.

2) Upscaling PLUM to a national repository

PLUM can be scaled to become a national non-profit community-led initiative supporting the public community to contribute to the scientific process. The open-source MIT license of the coding behind PLUM allows others to use/recreate the platform and thus uphold maintenance. However, we aim to work towards a national governance structure to secure a certain level of uniformity and patients' wishes. AJ and NN will start conversations with several partners, including NFU, KNAW, and the Dutch Patient Federation to host PLUM and discuss its potential as the primary directory for open access patient experience data.

Word count SEC51 (max 300): 300

Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

The PLUM platform brings together data sources making them searchable and interpretable. Data can either be structured or unstructured, so the challenge is in bringing it all together and still making sure that trends can be identified. For a conceptual system overview, see also figure 2. The target audience is any employee of University Medical Centers seeking to improve health care, contributing to health care education and in need of direction for their research. Besides manually analysing the available data in the platform, the platform proactively makes suggestions (intelligent trend detection) based on trends in the data by taking advantage of the possibilities that AI provides in interpreting structured and unstructured data.

The solution will be developed in house at UMCU and appropriate steps are taken to govern the quality. After reaching maturity the blueprint of the platform (documentation, code and infrastructure-as-code) will be provided as Open Source. To manage quality, mandatory Code Peer Reviews and security reviews are performed before publishing any changes. In addition to the industry standard best practices to manage the architecture and codequality of the platform, a key aspect is to monitor and validate the quality of the output. In order to safeguard this, a fixed input-dataset will be created and provided, that will allow users to repeatably validate the quality of the output.

The goal of the Software Quality Plan is to outline the processes, tools, and standards that will be used to ensure the quality of the code, including eg Azure IaC platform developed using Bicep. This plan aims to provide a framework for delivering high-quality code that meets the goals set for the project.

Quality Objectives;

- **Reliability:** Ensure the infrastructure is stable and performs as expected under various conditions, including but not limited to high usage, various types of input, various types of user-queries. As the solution uses AI language models to allow for data ingestion and data queries, specific measures are taken to safeguard against hallucinating and biases.
- **Security:** Implement best practices to protect the infrastructure from vulnerabilities and threats. Examples are Azure VNET implementation, Firewall, monitoring and logging
- **Maintainability:** Ensure the code is easy to understand, modify, and extend using best practices from Microsoft.
- **Compliance:** Adhere to industry standards and regulatory requirements, including but not limited to GDPR, AI Act.

Roles and Responsibilities;

- **Product Owner platform:** Oversees the solution and ensures adherence to the quality plan.
- **Software developer / Azure:** Develops and maintains the Bicep templates, ensuring they meet quality standards. Creates and maintains Azure DevOps deployment pipelines
- **Tester:** Conducts reviews and testing to ensure the solution meets quality objectives.
- **Solution Architect:** Ensures that security best practices are implemented and maintained, using industry standard and UMC U guidelines

Quality Standards;

- **Coding Standards:** Follow best practices for (Bicep) coding, including naming conventions, modularization, and documentation. Azure Verified Modules are used as Bicep blueprints.
- **Version Control:** Use Git for version control to track changes and facilitate collaboration.
- **Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD):** Implement Azure DevOps CI/CD pipelines to automate testing and deployment.

Quality Assurance Activities;

- **Code Reviews:** Conduct regular code reviews (PR requests) to ensure adherence to coding standards and identify potential (security-)issues early. Where possible automated code checking will be implemented (eg Dependabot)
- **Automated Testing:** Implement automated unit- and integration tests for code and Bicep templates, including security scans.
- **Manual Testing:** Perform manual testing to validate the solution in a real-world environment and validate the (functional-) output.
- **Performance Testing:** Conduct performance tests (load tests) to ensure the infrastructure can handle expected loads in terms of both data-ingestion and concurrent users.

Tools and Technologies;

- **React:** Front End development
- **Bicep:** Primary language for defining Azure infrastructure.
- **Azure DevOps:** For CI/CD pipelines and project management.
- **GitHub:** Source control /version control
- **Azure Security Center:** For security assessments and recommendations.

Continuous Improvement;

- **Feedback Loops:** Establish feedback loops with testers and users to gather input and make improvements. This includes external input (community feedback) after code has been shared as Open Source.
- **Retrospectives:** Conduct internal regular Agile retrospectives to review what went well and what can be improved.
- **Monitoring:** Use usage monitoring, logs and alerts to drive improvements to the platform while deployed

The solution will consist of the following key components:

- End user Front end.
- Keyword search, natural language search and intelligent trend detection.

- Data ingestion ETL.
- AI RAG module, using existing AI model(s) where possible, but possibly a bespoke AI model based on Dutch language and (medical-)terminology will need to be trained. - Data platform.

See also the Logical and technical system overview in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2: Logical system overview

The platform will be based on Microsoft Azure infrastructure components and will follow the Azure architecture best practices [2]. A high-level technical system overview is provided in Figure 3 but during implementation, further architecture improvements will be included to, for example, safeguard security and monitoring. For readability purposes these components are not included in the diagram.

Figure 3: Technical system overview

2. *How will you manage versioning of your software?*

Version control will be implemented using Git repositories in GitHub. These repositories will be split into the main components of the system, eg;

- Front End
- Infrastructure As Code (IaC) for search and RAG modules
- ETL / Data ingestion logic
- Test data, examples and documentation See also figure 2.

The releases will use Semantic Versioning as a versioning schema, allowing for a simple mechanism to manage (new) releases. In order to track the changes a changelog will be part of every repository.

3. *How will you make your software publicly available? What licence will your software have?*

The software, including the infrastructure configuration, will be released as Open Source using the MIT License. This will allow the community to use and extend the platform to their own benefit. In the future the platform might be adopted by a collaboration with NFU, KNAW and the Dutch Patient Federation, and a different Open Source licensing model could be used.

4. *How will users of your software be able to cite your software?*

The software and all related assets will be released in Git repositories, but no additional digital object identifier (DOI) will be provided. In order to make the resource easily findable, a CITATION.cff will be provided to improve machine indexing and findability.

5. *How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.*

In order to support the solution provided, a dedicated website will be hosted that contains all relevant information.

Key information here will be

- Generic product information, context and goals
- Functional documentation
- WIKI, containing technical documentation such as, Architecture documentation, System installation requirements, Installation manuals
- Knowledge base, for FAQ's

Where possible, we will use Search Engine Optimization (SEO) to elevate the findability of the solution and the relevant documentation.

6. *How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?*

The dedicated website, and also the GitHub repository, contain documentation on the process for submitting changes and improvements. These changes are merged with the main branch of the solution only after passing quality checks. The website and GitHub are also used to provide feedback on (bug-) reports from the community.

7. How will your software be tested?

The key components will be tested by type/technology.

- Configuration / Infrastructure As Code will use Unit Testing
- Integration testing will be possible using generic, anonymous, test datasets

8. How will you check that it respects the licences of libraries and dependencies it uses?

The Open-Source license will mandate that anyone extending/changing the solution will need to adhere to the same constraints as this solution, including but not limited to, making the changes publicly available, following the license rules imposed by components and referencing back to the source.

During development at the UMCU, validating licensing restrictions for 3rd party components will be part of the Peer Review (PR)

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

Software is packaged and distributed on GitHub by leveraging repositories for source code management, Git tags for versioning, and DevOps Pipelines / GitHub Releases to bundle compiled binaries or other assets with release notes. Developers automate builds and deployments using Azure DevOps or GitHub Actions, which can compile code, run tests, and publish packages to GitHub Packages (supporting npm, Docker, Maven, etc.) or external registries. Releases provide downloadable assets, while GitHub Packages enables dependency installation via tools like npm or docker. Azure DevOps is used to implement pipelines for infrastructure deployment to Azure.

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised? The software is released as Open Source and as such end user support will be organized by the party implementing the solution in-house. In terms of functional support, documentation will be provided that can be extended with online community support. For internal UMCU purposes, more details on the support of the solution can be found in chapter 5.1 Sustainability plan.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

UMCU has a structured and well-defined process of life cycle management (LCM). All developed products adhere to this process. A yearly budget is allocated per product to maintain, update and upgrade all components that the product consists of.

The team that develops the product, is responsible for the maintenance, according to the principle, “You build it, you own it.” This ensures knowledge of the infrastructure, back end and front end does not need to be transferred but is embedded in the team from the first moment.

Community input will be used to improve and maintain the solution, based on the Open-Source software and pushed changes from community developers.

Section 6: References

1. Science, N.P.O., *Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands. NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda*. 2022.
2. Microsoft. *Best practices in cloud applications*. 2025; Available from: <https://learn.microsoft.com/enus/azure/architecture/best-practices/index-best-practices>.

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.

